

A hierarchical Framework for Response Times and Signal Detection Theory

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Multiple Response Highlight

The nurse is assessing a 52-year-old male client with esophageal cancer who is receiving continuous enteral nutrition at 63 mL/h via a percutaneous gastrostomy tube.

The nurse notes the following:

Time: 0730

Vital signs:

blood pressure	98/72
heart rate	112
respirations	18
oxygen saturation	98% on room air
temperature	98.9° F (37.2° C)

Throat pain rated 2 on a scale of 0 (no pain) to 10 (severe pain)

Abdomen soft

Bowel sounds active x 4

Dry mucous membranes of mouth

Urine output 100 mL over the past 4 hours

Laboratory test results:

serum potassium	3.8 mEq/L (3.8 mmol/L)
serum sodium	147 mEq/L (147 mmol/L)
blood urea nitrogen	24 mg/dL (8.6 mmol/L)
hematocrit	50% (0.50)

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Multiple Response Highlight: Examinee 2

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Dry mucous membranes of mouth

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Multiple Response Highlight: Examinee 3

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Abdomen soft

Bowel sounds active x 4

Dry mucous membranes of mouth

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Scoring multiple response item types

- Corrected scoring
 - Subtract incorrect from correct

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Number of Cues Recognized

Multiple response item types

- Two component processes underlying responding behavior
 - A latent trait underlies sensitivity to relevant information
 - A latent trait underlies endorsement bias
- Signal-detection theory
 - Disentangles accuracy and conservative/liberal responding
 - 3 Examinees have the same accuracy, but different responding biases

Scoring multiple response item types

- Signal-detection theory

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- Signal-detection theory (DeCarlo, 1998; 2010; 2011; 2012)

$$P(y = 1|S) = \Phi((\Psi_S - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|N) = \Phi((\Psi_N - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi(-c + dX)$$

$$P(y_{ij} = 1|c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi\left(-c_i + d_i\mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j\mathbf{X})\right)$$

Response Time

- Examinees
 - What is the relationship between sensitivity and speed?
 - Are higher ability examinees faster/slower?
 - What is the relationship between responding criterion and speed?
 - Are cautious and conservative examinees slower/faster?
- Items
 - Do difficult items require more time?
 - What is the relationship between responding behavior and time?

Response Time

- van der Linden₍₂₀₀₇₎ proposed a hierarchical approach for investigating speed/accuracy tradeoff
 - Two component models: IRT and response time
 - Linked through population level parameters
- The current study takes a similar approach by linking the SDT model with a response time model

Response Time

SDT model:

$$P(y_{ij} = 1 | c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi \left(-c_i + d_i \mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j \mathbf{X}) \right)$$

Response time model: $t_{ij} \sim LN(\beta_j - \tau_i, \gamma_j^{-2})$

Population level model: $(c, d, \tau) \sim MVN(\mu_{cd\tau}, \Sigma_{cd\tau})$

$$(\alpha, \delta, \beta, \gamma) \sim MVN(\mu_{\alpha\delta\beta\gamma}, \Sigma_{\alpha\delta\beta\gamma})$$

Empirical Example

- Licensing exam in allied health
 - 39 technology enhanced items
 - Over 1900 observations per item
- Fitted models:
 - Hierarchical Rasch PCM with Lognormal Response Time model
 - Hierarchical SDT with Lognormal Response Time Model
- Stochastic estimation
 - Both models converged quickly
 - Attributed to the response time model

SDT Ability and PCM Ability

SDT Criterion and PCM Ability

Processing Speed and SDT Ability

Processing Speed and SDT Criterion

SDT and PCM Item Difficulty

SDT Item Difficulty and Criterion

PCM Item Difficulty and Time Intensity

SDT Item Difficulty and Time Intensity

SDT Item Criterion and Time Intensity

Conclusion

- SDT disentangles item accuracy and responding bias
- Hierarchical response time model provides richer description of responding behavior
 - Examinees
 - Items
- Items promoting conservative behavior yield longer response times
 - Only responses surpassing conservative threshold are endorsed.
 - Accumulation of evidence takes a longer time

THANKS